

ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF VARIATIONS IN WEATHER CONDITIONS ON SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS

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ABSTRACT

Using a quantitative research approach and secondary variables on climate change, GDP, and India's population, this study investigates the impact of climate change on the Indian economy. The impact of climatic factors on India's economic development was examined using statistical approaches such as Regression Analysis. It turns out, according to the study's findings, that population increase in India was impacted by climatic change factors (such as rainfall and temperature), but rainfall and population had little effect on economic development separately. There was also a strong positive association between GDP and population, as well as a negative correlation between temperature and that same measure of population growth. Researchers found that climate change has a big impact on India's economic development, since higher temperatures and more rain might boost agricultural productivity, which could help fuel the country's economic expansion.

Keywords: whether variation, Economic growth, population pearson correlation

INTRODUCTION

Combating the harmful effects of climate change on ecosystems is an important part of contemporary global policy. Nations throughout the world are concerned about climate change, in part because it is caused by human activity (Anbumozhi, et al., 2012). The environment on our planet is always changing. Despite this, Earth's climate has changed dramatically during the last century. This has had rapid and widespread harmful consequences since the earth's temperature has risen dramatically. Human activity, especially in the areas of industrialization and industry, may be blamed for some of the problems associated with climate change (Joshi and Linke, 2011).

Succinctly put, climate change (also known as global warming) is an increase in the world's universal mean temperature that will have serious consequences for the planet's ecosystem. Because of the overuse of natural resources and the high level of pollution, it has a negative impact on people's health and well-being. As global mean temperatures rise, it's possible that human health and safety may suffer (Ghosh, 2013).

According to Puthucherry (2012), South Asia, particularly India, would be severely impacted by climate change over the next several years due to the country's unique geography. Since the country is rapidly depleting its mineral resources and damaging its ecology mostly as a consequence of urbanisation, various industrial operations, and economic growth, global warming is projected to severely harm this area. India's attempt to protect rapidly depleting natural resources is beset by socio-economic and climatic problems. Every day, the quality of the air and water decreases due to an increase in various types of contaminants in the environment. Global warming will have the greatest impact on the nation's coastline eco-systems, agricultural productivity, and biodiversity, according to the report. A natural calamity like Uttarakhand floods and landslides, which occurred in 2013, or the Chennai flooding of 2015 or 2016, has previously struck these areas with devastating results. Intense rains, heat waves, and prolonged dry periods have all been documented.

On the other hand, the negative consequences of global warming are not felt uniformly around the world. Because of their sensitivity to the unfavourable impact of rising sea levels on water resources, the environment, agriculture, food production, fisheries, and general human well-being, poor countries and people bear the brunt of global warming's negative consequences (Stern and Stern 2007). Rising economies must diversify their economies and improve the quality of life for their citizens if they are to increase economic growth and reduce poverty. As a result of their actions, GHG emissions will rise, contributing to climate change. As a result, the emphasis of this article is on climate change and its implications for the Indian economy.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Some economic activities that erode the ozone layer in the name of improving living lead to global warming through depleting the ozone layer. Urbanization, industrialisation, air pollution, improper disposal of hazardous waste, and oil spills are examples of such activities. However, the negative impact of global warming is not evenly distributed between countries. Most of the detrimental consequences of climate change will fall on the less developed countries, which have emitted much less GHGs in comparison to their reliance on fossil fuels. As a result, global warming is becoming a major source of worry for the global economy. This article investigates the impact of climate change on India's economy.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To evaluate the impact of climate change on India's economy

HYPOTHESIS

There would be no big impact on India's economy from climate change

LITERATURE REVIEW

Climate change may cause some sectors of the economy to expand faster than others, while the composition and size of GDP in different countries will improve as a result. The long-term growth prospects of the country are also harmed by climatic changes. Furthermore, the effects of climate change are not uniform across nations; according to Lucas & Valente (2011), agriculture, coastal areas, and the elderly are the most vulnerable groups.

According to the Stern et al (2007) assessment, global temperatures are expected to rise by 2°C to 3°C over the next fifty years, which might have a negative impact on economic growth since it could damage water quality, human well-being, and food production. It was also estimated that these negative effects will eat away at about 5% of global GDP each year. According to Parry et al. (2007), the snow cover and glaciers are expected to decrease, resulting in water shortages. If the global mean temperature rises by 1.5-2.5°C, over 20-30% of plant and animal species may go extinct, according to scientists.

Hitz and Smith (2004) assert that economic growth and energy use are closely linked. It is clear that increasing energy use leads to an increase in greenhouse gas emissions (GHG). According to estimates, developed countries are responsible for around three-quarters of global CO₂ emissions. This conclusion demonstrates that environmental degradation has an impact on economic development. Ever-increasing GHG emissions in developing countries, particularly in an expanding economy like India, have raised concerns about climate change's impact on economic development in the modern era. According to Hope (2006), climate change may have short-term benefits in some industrialised economies, but it will be harmful over the long term.

According to Pindyck (2011), temperature variations have a negative influence on GDP because of both theoretical and empirical evidence. According to Mendelshon et al. (2007), agriculture is extremely important to the economies of most emerging countries. They're more exposed to temperature changes because many of them live in lower-income areas with less affluent mindsets. A rise in temperature may have a negative impact on agricultural productivity because it emphasises the idea that low-attitude places are more likely to experience extreme heat, which is unsuitable for most forms of agriculture.

Warmer weather can have significant effects on agricultural production, farm profitability, and food security, according to a study by Gornall et al (2010). Depending on where you live, the effects of climate change can vary widely. In high and middle latitudes, agricultural production is supposed to rise and spread further north; however, this is not always the case, especially in countries located in humid climates. According to the experts, a

two-degree increase in temperature in intermediate and high areas would improve wheat cultivation by almost 10%, while it would decrease in lower places.

According to Ebkom and Dahlberg (2008), industrial expansion has connections to ecosystems and climate change, as well as certain challenges. Ecosystems provide two critical services in terms of economic growth. By providing raw materials for manufacturing, it helps to keep prices low. It also serves as a catchment area for pollution agents emitted during a variety of economic activity. Ecosystems are also likened to a place where hazardous and non-hazardous waste is stored for safekeeping.

Mahfuz (2014) found that the effects of climate change are harming the economy in Southern Asia, with a potential to reduce GDP by 8.8% by the year 2100 as a result of dangerous climatic change. It was also stressed by him that countries within the region must take necessary measures to cope with climate change and avoid economic difficulties.

METHODOLOGY

This research utilised a quantitative research design and secondary data on climate change variables, GDP, and India's population. Statistics such as Multiple Regression Analysis and Pearson Correlation were performed to see if climate variables affect India's economic growth. The data was obtained from the World Bank data repository and SPSS 12.0 was used for data analysis. GDP is the dependent variable, while rainfall, temperature, and population are the independent factors.

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Table 2: Model Summary

Model	R	R²	Adjusted R²	Std. Error
1	.785	.616	.623	.17594

Predictors: log Population, log Rainfall, log Temp

Table 3: ANOVA Result

Model	S.S.	d.f.	M.S.	F	Sig.
Regression	3.436	3	1.113	31.532	.000
Residual	1.045	32	.034		
Total	4.481	35			

Predictors: log Population, log Rainfall, log Temp

Dependent Variable: log GDP

Table 4: Independent Effect

Model		Unstandardized Coeff		Standardized Coeff	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.392	1.592		-.271	.705
	Log Temp	-.189	.141	-.168	-1.456	.156
	logRainfall	1.475	.751	.169	1.912	.000
	logPopulation	.158	.026	.682	6.089	.000

a Dependent Variable: logGDP

The study's findings reveal that temperature, rainfall, and population all have a substantial impact on GDP. The fluctuation in GDP may be attributed to three factors: rainfall, temperature, and population. Aside from that, rainfall had a large independent impact (p=.000) as did population (p=.682; t=6.089; p=.000), but temperature had no effect (p=.156; p=.168; t=-1.456; p>.156). To put it another way: Rainfall, temperature, and population all play a role in India's economic growth, but only rainfall and population have a large impact, while temperature has little effect..

Table 5: Correlation Matrix of Variables

	logGDP	logTemp	logRainfall	logPopulation
logGDP	1			
logTemp	-.645(**)	1		
logRainfall	.197	.080	1	
logPopulation	.790(**)	-.653(**)	.029	1

The correlation result reveals a strong and statistically significant positive association between population and GDP (r =.790), as well as a significant negative relationship between temperature and GDP (r = -.645), among other things. Furthermore, population was shown to be favourably significant, whilst temperature was found to be adversely significant.

CONCLUSION

This research investigates the economic impact of climate change in India. Using multiple regression analysis, it was discovered that rainfall and temperature, both of which are influenced by climate change, together with India's population had a substantial impact on economic growth, whereas temperature had no effect. Climate change may offer some short-term benefits in industrialised economies, but it will be harmful over the long term, according to Hope (2006). Temperature variations have been shown to have a negative influence on GDP, according to Pindyck (2011).

Another finding of this study was that there is a strong positive association between the population's income and GDP, as well as a negative correlation between temperature and income. As Gornall et al. (2010) found, rising temperatures have the potential to have significant effects on agricultural production, farm income, and food security. The findings of this study show that climate change is having a big impact on India's economic growth, as higher temperatures and more rain could boost agricultural productivity, which in turn could contribute to the country's growing economy.

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